

METHODS OF TEACHING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO SOLVE COMPLEX PROBLEMS

Sh. Uskanova

1st year master's student. Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami and United Educational Programm of Kazan Federal University

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Abstract. *Traditionally, in the process of learning to solve word problems, most students have difficulties in mastering the material, so one of the most important goals in the initial course of mathematics is the selection of appropriate didactic material, techniques and methods aimed at developing the ability to solve mathematical problems. This, in turn, contributes to the formation of knowledge and skills in schoolchildren that are necessary in everyday life when solving certain problem situations. At the first stage of teaching mathematics in primary school, students are introduced to the concept of a mathematical problem, subsequently expanding their knowledge on this topic, children learn to clarify various aspects of the relationships in the life around them. Solving problems allows the child to understand the practical significance of those mathematical concepts that he masters in the initial course of mathematics, gives the opportunity to apply the studied theoretical provisions in practice.*

Keywords: *methodology, teaching, students, primary school, solutions, complex problems, mathematics, teaching, upbringing, education.*

Formation of thinking and development of intellect in primary school students is one of the most important didactic tasks of an educational institution. An important component of the process of forming intellect in primary school students is logical thinking. Among the natural sciences, mathematics has the greatest potential for forming logical thinking in students. An analysis of the State Standard of Primary General Education in Mathematics allows us to conclude: the formation of logical thinking in schoolchildren is an important goal of school education at different levels of studying mathematics.

At present, in our country, in connection with socio-economic changes, new tasks appear before educational institutions. The dynamism of the formation of society is closely connected with the renewal of the entire education system, rethinking the tasks, content and technology of the learning process, developing fresh approaches to its organization.

The formation of individuality, the disclosure of the inclinations and predispositions of the student are considered a strategic task of the educational process, because only logically thinking, erudite and intelligent people have every chance of self-realization. It is impossible to imagine a modern educated person without meaningful study of mathematics. Primary school is usually considered the first step in mastering the full school course of mathematics in general. At this stage, the mathematical course includes the basics of arithmetic, elements of geometry, and the beginnings of algebra. The deepest, long-lasting mathematical knowledge is acquired in the process of students' search work. This requires a teacher who is able to implement, actively influence the process of mastering mathematical material by younger students and develop the ability to use this knowledge in practice[9].

One of the main tasks of the initial stage of mathematics is to teach primary school students to solve various mathematical problems, and then apply their knowledge in everyday life. Before giving students the opportunity to independently find solutions to various problems, it is necessary to first introduce children to the principles and order of their solution. It is important to teach children not just to solve certain problems in the same way, but to approach each problem creatively, to be able to solve the same problem in different ways, and then to choose the simplest and most suitable for this problem. To do this, it is necessary to develop logical and creative thinking in students[6].

The traditional approach to mathematical education of primary school students often consists in organizing their activities to master ready-made knowledge and skills, which sometimes inhibits the development of children's intelligence, primarily logical thinking. Therefore, by teaching children to master the ability to consider different approaches to solving a problem, we will have a significant impact on their interest in the subject and on the development of logical thinking.

Thinking is a complex and multifaceted mental activity, therefore, the types of thinking are distinguished on different grounds. Depending on the extent to which the thought process is based on perception, representation or concept, there are three main types of thinking:

- Object-active (or visual-active) - is typical of small children, who thus learn about the world, acquiring some life experience, and animals. Thinking about objects means acting, manipulating them. Looking at, touching, listening, maybe even sniffing and tasting.

- Visual-figurative - is typical for preschoolers and partly for younger schoolchildren. The work of the right hemisphere of the brain is mainly visual processing of information, although it can also be auditory (hearing). In adulthood, visual-figurative thinking (also called artistic type) is characteristic of people with a leading right hemisphere, creative professions, for example, artists, actors.

- Verbal-logical (abstract) – characterizes high school students and adults. As a person develops and matures, he or she learns to speak and think logically. Pictures and images, direct perception (see, hear, touch, smell, taste) are replaced by verbal designations and logical chains of reasoning leading to certain conclusions. Many people's left hemisphere begins to work more, people perceive and interpret the world: life situations and various phenomena in words, trying to logically comprehend what is happening around them. Right-hemisphere (figurative, emotional thinking) also does not go away, and everything that was perceived visually-figuratively and objectively-effectively, together with the emotional coloring, is stored in the person's subconscious. However, most people do not remember their childhood and especially childhood experiences, because as an adult, a person thinks logically, in words, and not in images and pictures, as in childhood.

- Logical thinking is a process in which a person resorts to logical concepts based on evidence and prudence. Its goal is to obtain a well-founded conclusion based on the "given", that is, specific premises. There are three types of logical reasoning:

- Figurative-logical - in this case, the situation is "played out" by the imagination, while we recall the images of the objects involved or the features of the phenomena. Yes, this can be called imagination.

- Abstract - here it is already more complicated, categories, objects or connections are used that do not exist in reality (that is, abstractions). Verbal, in which people share their logical

judgments with others. Here, not only a tendency to analyze is important, but also literate speech. Having learned what logic is, let's see how it can be useful in life.

Mental operations are varied. These are analysis and synthesis, comparison, abstraction, concretization, generalization, classification. Which logical operations a person uses will depend on the task and the nature of the information that he subjects to mental processing.

- Analysis is a mental decomposition of a whole into parts or a mental selection of its sides, actions, relationships from a whole.

- Synthesis is the opposite process of thought to analysis, it is the unification of parts, properties, actions, relationships into a single whole.

- Comparison is the establishment of similarities and differences between objects and phenomena. Comparison is based on analysis. Before comparing objects, it is necessary to select one or more of their features, by which the comparison will be made. Comparison can be one-sided, or incomplete, and multi-sided, or more complete. Comparison, like analysis and synthesis, can be of different levels - superficial and deeper. In this case, a person's thought goes from external signs of similarity and difference to internal ones, from the visible to the hidden, from the phenomenon to the essence[14-15].

- Abstraction is a process of mental abstraction from some features, aspects of the concrete with the purpose of better understanding it. A person mentally singles out some feature of an object and examines it in isolation from all other features, temporarily distracting himself from them. Isolated study of individual features of an object while simultaneously abstracting from all others helps a person to more deeply understand the essence of things and phenomena. Thanks to abstraction, a person was able to break away from the individual, the concrete and rise to the highest level of knowledge - scientific theoretical thinking.

Concretization is a process that is the opposite of abstraction and is inextricably linked with it. Concretization is the return of thought from the general and abstract to the concrete with the purpose of revealing the content.

Mental activity is always aimed at obtaining some result. A person analyzes objects, compares them, abstracts individual properties in order to identify what they have in common, to discover the patterns that govern their development, to master them. Developing logical thinking in the learning process means:

- Developing in students the ability to compare observed objects, find common properties and differences in them; developing the ability to highlight the essential properties of objects and abstract them from secondary, inessential ones;

- Teaching children to dismember (analyze) an object into its component parts in order to understand each component part and to combine (synthesize) mentally dismembered objects into a single whole, while understanding the interaction of parts and the object as a single whole, teaching schoolchildren to draw correct conclusions from observations or facts, and be able to verify these conclusions;

- Instilling the ability to generalize facts, to develop in students the ability to convincingly prove the truth of their judgments and refute false conclusions;

- Ensuring that students' thoughts are presented clearly, consistently, without contradiction, and reasonably.

During the transition from visual-figurative thinking, which is the main one at this point, to verbal-logical thinking, the thinking of a primary school child is at a turning point in development. The main work for the development of logical thinking should be carried out with a task. After all, any task contains great opportunities for the development of logical thinking[8].

The first stage in teaching problem solving in the initial course of mathematics is to introduce students to the concept of a mathematical problem, its structure, and then its types. At this stage, the main goal of the teacher is to teach children to work with a problem. Working with a problem means, first of all, understanding its structure, being able to distinguish between the given and the sought-after, determining its main question, finding the most rational way to solve a particular problem, and being able to independently compose problems based on the proposed parameters. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to be guided primarily by the principle of accessibility in learning. This is, first of all, a harmoniously selected educational and methodological complex. On the basis of which the learning process is built.

The first acquaintance with a complex task and its structure looks like this:

There are several ways to solve this.

If the area of the figure in the picture is 680 cm², find X using the given dimensions.

Each task is a unity of condition and goal. If one of these components is missing, then there is no task. It is very important to keep this in mind in order to analyze the text of the task in compliance with such unity. This means that the analysis of the task condition must be correlated with the task question and vice versa, the task question must be analyzed in a targeted manner with the condition. They cannot be separated, since they constitute a single whole. A mathematical task is a coherent laconic story in which the values of some quantities are introduced and it is proposed to find other unknown values of quantities that depend on the data and are related to them by certain relationships specified in the condition[11].

"For a text arithmetic problem, various authors offer the following definitions.

- An arithmetic problem is a requirement to find the numerical value of a certain quantity if the numerical values of other quantities are given and there is a relationship that links these quantities both among themselves and with the desired one (Bogdanovich M.V.).

- In the life around us, many such situations arise that are related to numbers and require arithmetic operations on them - these are problems (Bantova M.A.).

- A problem is a question formulated in words, the answer to which can be obtained using arithmetic operations (Moro M.I., Pyshkalo A.M.).

- A text problem is a description of a certain situation (situations) in natural language with a requirement to give a quantitative characteristic of some component of this situation, to establish the presence or absence of some relationship between its components or to determine the type of this relationship (Stoilova L.P., Pyshkalo A.M.).

- Any problem is a requirement or question to which an answer must be found, relying on and taking into account the conditions that are specified in it (Friedman L.M., Turetsky E.N.)

- In the introductory course of mathematics, the concept of "problem" is usually used when talking about arithmetic problems. They are formulated in the form of a text that reflects quantitative relationships between real objects (Istomina N.B.)

- Text arithmetic problems are problems that have everyday, physical content and are solved using arithmetic operations (Drozd V.L.)

Thus, there is no clear definition of a text arithmetic problem, only its concept is introduced, and, according to Metelisy N.V., this concept is primary (undefinable). He notes that "a problem is an undefinable concept and in the broadest sense of the word means something that requires execution, solution. Sometimes a problem is understood as an exercise that is performed, solved by means of inference, calculation, etc." [2, p. 4-5]

In primary school, the structure of a text problem is divided into: a condition and a requirement (question).

- A condition is a part that communicates information about objects and their quantities, about the relationships between them, and sets quantitative characteristics of quantities (their numerical values).

- A requirement is an indication of what needs to be found. It can be expressed by a sentence in an imperative or interrogative form.

In the short diagram of the problem statement, the arrows of direct and inverse proportionality are placed differently.

To achieve any goal, it is necessary to set and solve a number of problems. In the initial course of mathematics, as was said earlier, one of the main goals is to develop the ability to solve problems, both simple and composite (complex), including those with proportional values. In this paper, we consider exactly this type of problem. In primary grades, work is carried out on groups of problems, the solution of which is based on the same connections between the data and the desired, and they differ in specific content and numerical data. Groups of such problems are called problems of the same type; in this work, we consider problems with proportional quantities. In various primary education programs, approaches to teaching the solution of problems with proportional quantities have their own methodological features. [5].

The educational and methodological complex harmony for a four-year primary school was created at the Department of Mathematics and Methods of Teaching It in Primary Education of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami. The program of M. Dzhumayev is based on a methodological concept that expresses the need for targeted and systematic work on the formation of mental activity techniques in younger students: analysis and synthesis,

comparison, classification, analogy and generalization, in the process of mastering mathematical content.

It is the listed methods of mental activity that form the basis of the activity associated with solving text problems.

According to M. Dzhumaev, problems with proportional quantities are especially difficult for younger students, since the concept of proportional dependence is not a subject of special study and assimilation in primary school.

"The connections between proportional quantities are revealed by solving simple problems of finding one of the quantities based on data corresponding to the values of two other quantities (for example, a problem of finding the cost based on known price and quantity)" [10].

"Therefore, when solving simple problems with proportional quantities, it is advisable to use both the already considered methodological techniques for teaching problem solving, and those techniques that help students develop ideas about the proportional dependence of quantities.

Among these techniques, we can name:

- Changing one of the data in the problem
- Comparing the results of solving problems in which one of the data changes
- Interpreting the problem in the form of a diagram, writing the problem in a table.
- Analysis of the texts of problems with missing and extra data" [9].

The mathematics program of M. Dzhumaev is compiled in accordance with the age and psychological characteristics of primary school students, aimed at the successful assimilation of the mandatory minimum content of education in mathematics, allows for the optimal organization of the study of the program material, and maintains the interest of students in the subject. The authors took the classical methodology of studying mathematics as a basis and adapted it for modern children, including the author's methodological discoveries in the program.

Text problems are included in the content of the program material along with other sections. Along with simple problems, some types of compound problems are introduced in the first year of teaching mathematics. According to the authors of the program, this helps children get rid of the template when choosing an action and a solution method. The authors have also thought out a system of logical problems, tasks for attention, memory, imagination, without the development of which it is impossible to deeply assimilate the program material, further education of schoolchildren.

In the third grade, junior schoolchildren learn to use various methods of encoding the conditions of a text problem. In the process of working on a text problem, the student makes a brief record of the problem using various forms: a table, a drawing, a diagram, etc.; selects and justifies the choice of actions to solve problems on multiple comparison, on finding the fourth proportional (by the method of reduction to one, by the comparison method), problems on calculating the cost (price, quantity, cost), on finding a time interval (beginning, end, duration of an event). The student can compose a problem based on its brief record, presented in various forms (table, diagram, drawing, etc.), evaluate the correctness of the course of solving the problem; check the solution of the problem in different ways [13].

In the fourth grade, all those lines of work with problems that were started in the second and third grades continue. The main emphasis in the fourth grade is on solving compound problems with quantities, on motion and inverse problems. Particular attention is paid to solving combinatorial problems by enumerating all possible options, using a tree of options, tables. Thus,

having analyzed 3 teaching and methodological complexes School of Russia, Harmony, Perspective, we came to the conclusion that work with text problems, namely problems with proportional quantities, is carried out in each teaching and methodological complex. The ability of younger students to solve problems of this type is formed with the help of different methodological techniques, each of the programs offers its own solution method and type of recording.

In accordance with the set tasks, based on the analysis of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, a conceptual apparatus for the problem under study was identified, theoretical material for working on a composite problem was systematized, as well as methods for working on problems with proportional quantities, an analysis of the methodological aspects of teaching how to solve problems with proportional quantities in various teaching and methodological kits was conducted, and tasks aimed at developing the ability to solve problems with proportional quantities were developed and tested.

Having considered the psychological, mathematical and methodological foundations of teaching how to solve problems with proportional quantities, we can conclude that teaching primary school students how to solve problems with proportional dependence, as well as how to solve text problems in general, should be based on the creative potential of children, its search and improvement. It is important to teach schoolchildren to think beyond the proposed, to perform logical operations, analysis, synthesis, etc., and not to allow templates in teaching.

In the course of practical activities, tasks were developed and tested aimed at developing the ability of primary school students to solve problems with proportional quantities. In our opinion, at the beginning of working with problems on proportional dependence, it is necessary to clearly form the concept of both quantities in general and the properties of quantities and their dependencies in schoolchildren. In this case, we are talking about direct and inverse proportionality between quantities. In problems of the "price/quantity/cost" type, it is important to show that the cost of any items directly depends on their quantity, while the price is a fixed value. Particular attention when working with problems of this type should be given to problems on movement. It is especially difficult for schoolchildren to understand the dependence of the time of movement of any object on its speed, etc.

The methodology for solving problems on proportional dependence proposed by us has proven its effectiveness. Thus, it must be said that the goal of the final qualifying work has been achieved, the tasks set have been solved.

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